

Study on the Use of Floating Photovoltaics on Kourna Lake, Western Crete, Greece

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ABSTRACT:

Installation of floating solar photovoltaic systems on the surface of water bodies has been developed rapidly in recent years worldwide. However, installation of floating photovoltaics in water reservoirs in Greece has not been reported so far. Kourna lake is the only natural lake in Crete located in the western part of the island in an idyllic and environmentally protected site while several touristic activities have been developed locally. The characteristics of the lake are mentioned and various parameters of a floating photovoltaic system which can be installed have been evaluated. A floating photovoltaic system with nominal power at 2.42 MW_p can be installed on its surface with coverage ratio 5% generating 3.6 GWh annually. If the coverage ratio of the surface is at 10% the nominal power of the installed floating photovoltaic system will be at 4.83 MW_p while the annually generated electricity will be at 7.24 GWh corresponding at 0.24% of the power demand in the island in 2018. The advantages and the drawbacks of the novel floating energy system have been stated. The acceptance of the abovementioned solar energy system from the local community is a prerequisite for its successful installation avoiding local conflicts and protests related with the co-existence of the current touristic activities with solar power generation in the lake.

Keywords: Crete-Greece, ecology, electricity generation, floating photovoltaics, Kourna lake.

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INTRODUCTION

The installation of floating solar photovoltaics on water bodies has been developed rapidly in the last ten years worldwide [1], [2]. Their installation on the surface of water reservoirs is an attractive option compared to their installation on the soil or on rooftop of buildings particularly in densely populated countries with limited land availability [3], [4], [5]. Apart from their installation on man-made water reservoirs their installation on natural lakes has been studied in various countries [6], [7], [8], [9]. The installation of floating photovoltaics (FPVs) in various water reservoirs in Greece has been studied [3], [10] although there are not installations of FPV systems so far in the country.

The aim of the current work is the investigation of the possibility of installing floating photovoltaics in the natural lake of Kourna located in Western Crete, Greece.

The structure of the text is as follows: After the literature review the possibility of using FPVs on water reservoirs is discussed. Next, the possibility of using FPVs on water bodies in Crete is examined followed by an assessment of their installation in Kourna lake. After that, the advantages and drawbacks of their use in Kourna lake are mentioned while the text ends with discussion of the findings, the conclusions drawn and the citation of the references used.

The text is innovative since the existing studies regarding the use of FPVs on water bodies and natural lakes in Greece are limited. It fills an existing gap regarding the alternative installation of FPVs on water bodies and natural lakes in the island of Crete, Greece. The current research could

be useful to policy makers, to public and municipal authorities, to energy companies as well as to the local society which has developed several economic activities related mainly with tourism in Kourna lake.

LITERATURE SURVEY

The impacts of a FPV on the water quality in the Oostvoornse lake, the Netherlands have been studied [6]. The authors stated that use of FPVs results in reduced light intensity by 73% to 100% while the water temperature and the dissolved oxygen were only slightly affected. They also mentioned that the size of the floating solar-PV system was in the range of 350 m² to 600 m² while the size of the lake was 270 ha. The ecology of Kournas lake, Crete has been studied [11]. The author stated that five species of freshwater fishes were detected while many birds were stopping in the lake during their migration. The massive use of FPV on lake Nasser, Egypt has been studied [7]. The authors stated that the lake is the second largest man-made freshwater lake in the world with surface at 5,000 km² while due to high temperatures the water evaporation from the lake is very high. They also mentioned that if only 20% of the lake is covered with FPV the generated green electricity could meet around 16% of the EU power needs while the water saving due to lower evaporation losses is equal to around 20%-25% of the annual water demand in Egypt. The technology of FPV has been reviewed [1]. The authors stated that 1% coverage of the global water reservoirs with FPVs represents a potential solar power capacity at 404 GW_p. They also mentioned that FPVs have several advantages compared to ground-mounted solar-PVs. The potential of using FPV on mine pit lakes focused on an open-pit limestone mine in South Korea has been investigated [12]. The authors stated that existing studies related with installation of FPV on abandoned mine pit lakes are limited worldwide. They also mentioned that the annual reduction of carbon emissions due to the abovementioned FPV installation is twice the reduction achieved by reforestation of the abandoned mine site. The possibility of installing a FPV system on the Skadar lake, Montenegro for supplying electricity in an Aluminium plant in Montenegro has been studied [8]. The authors stated that the proposed FPV, at 90 MW_p, can provide a significant amount of electricity in the Aluminium plant having also positive economic performance. The possibility of installing FPVs on mountain artificial lakes has been investigated [9]. The authors stated that mountains have favorable conditions for solar electricity generation while their natural ecosystems are fragile. They also mentioned that the installation of FPV in mountains should avoid conflicts with the local society and the related stakeholders. The feasibility of installing FPV over lakes in Bengaluru city, India has been studied [13]. The authors stated that the city is densely populated and the installation of solar-PV systems on rooftops of buildings is difficult. They mentioned that the installation of FPV on the 32 lakes within the city limits with a coverage ratio at 0.5-0.6 could meet around 26% of the city's annual peak power. The impacts of FPV systems on water temperature and stratification with reference the lake Maiwald, South Germany have been investigated [14]. The authors stated that the installation of a FPV system with 2% coverage hardly causes any changes to the thermal characteristics of the lake. They also mentioned that underneath the FPV, a 37% reduction of the irradiance on the water and an average 23% reduction in near-surface wind speed at module height were observed. The use of FPV in natural lakes focusing on the natural lake, Laguna de Bay, Philippines has been studied [15]. The author stated that there are various uncertainties regarding the environmental impacts of installing FPV in natural lakes. Four small pilot FPV systems have been installed on the lake monitoring their environmental impacts on the physical, chemical and biological parameters. The physical, chemical and biological parameters of the water in Mahoni lake, Indonesia to evaluate the effect of FPVs have been analyzed [2]. The authors stated that FPVs reduce the average water temperature, the dissolved oxygen, the total dissolved solids and the chlorophyll concentration while they did not change the total phosphorus concentration in the water. The impacts of FPVs installed on water bodies to climate change mitigation have been investigated [4]. The authors stated that low surface coverage has negligible effect on the thermal structure of water bodies while high coverages have major impacts on thermal characteristics. The possibility of using floating solar photovoltaic panels on water bodies in the island of Crete, Greece has been examined [3]. The author stated that the installation of FPV on two major water reservoirs in the island with coverage ratio 10% could generate 46.37 GWh_{el}/year which correspond at 1.52% of the annual power demand in Crete while 528,000 M³/year of water could be saved due to reduced water evaporation. The potential of using FPV on

water bodies in continental Spain has been evaluated [5]. The authors stated that Spain could meet about 31% of its electricity demand by covering only 10% of the available water surface. They also mentioned that if natural water bodies are excluded the installation of FPV in man-made water reservoirs could meet around 22% of the county's electricity demand. The power system in Crete has been analyzed [16]. It is stated that the total electricity consumption in 2018 in the island was 3,043 GWh_{el} while the share of RES in the energy mix was at 21.2%. The impacts of climate change in Greece have been assessed [17]. The authors accentuated that relatively small decreases in the mean annual precipitation increase the risk in water reservoirs regarding the annual water supply and the power generation. They also mentioned that the adaptive capacity in Greece is not high and serious actions should be taken for climate change mitigation and adaptation. The Greek National Plan for Energy and Climate has been analyzed [18]. The authors stated that there are several drawbacks in the country's National Plan related with the proposed energy mix, the energy storage, the energy savings, the future energy prices et cetera. They proposed the delay of the energy transition to better prepare it. The status of FPVs in Southern European countries has been analyzed [19]. The authors stated that Southern European countries have excellent climate conditions for higher use of solar energy. They also mentioned that FPVs have many advantages while its main drawback is the higher installation cost compared to ground-mounted solar-PVs. The potential ecological impacts of FPVs on lakes' biodiversity have been studied [20]. The authors stated that existing research has highlighted the fact that FPVs reduce the light intensity, the wind speed and the water temperature on natural lakes. They also mentioned that changes in physical parameters like temperature, oxygen concentration et cetera may alter several regulatory processes affecting the web food in lakes. A report related with the impacts of FPV on fishing has been published [21]. The authors stated that existing studies indicate that that the impacts of FPVs on fish population in large water bodies is insignificant. They also mentioned that FPVs can be a solution for a sustainable food-energy-water nexus. The impacts of foam-based photovoltaics on natural lakes have been studied [22]. The authors stated that terminal lakes are disappearing worldwide because of direct and indirect human activities. They investigated the impacts of FPVs on water volume changes in Walker lake, Nevada, USA. Their results indicated that FPVs with coverage ratio 50% can reduce the water evaporation in the lake at 52,000,000 M³/year. The potential of solar power plants installed on pit lakes in former lignite mines has been analyzed [23]. It is stated that the economic potential for installing FPVs on pit lakes in former lignite mines in Germany is 2.74 GW_p. It is also mentioned that the cost of power generation for FPV systems is about 10-15% higher than the cost of conventional ground-mounted solar-PV power plants. Several characteristics of Kourna lake have been reported [24]. It is stated that the lake is the only natural lake in Crete with fresh water protected under Natura 2000 regulations. Its max length is 1,087 m, its max width 889 m while its water volume changes over the year with a max at 7,500,000 m³. Its max depth is 22.5 m while the water flow is controlled from a water dam constructed in 1962. More than 40 species of birds have been recorded in the lake while in the broader area protected under Natura 2000 regulations more than 130 species of birds, including migratory birds, have been detected. Several characteristics of Kourna lake have been reported [25]. The lake is located in municipality of Apokoronas in a distance of 47 km from the city of Chania. It is one of the few areas in Crete where there is abundant fresh water throughout the year. The circumference of the lake is about 3.5 km while its bottom is 3 m below sea level. The long history of Kourna lake has been studied [26]. The authors stated that interactions between climate, human activities, erosion, vegetation and fire in Kourna lake have a history of more than 10,000 years. They also mentioned that traditional Mediterranean uses like local olive tree cultivation played a major role in the landscape of the area around the lake. A report related to the global market of FPVs has been published [27]. According to this report FPVs offer new possibilities for solar electricity generation especially in countries with high population density and competing uses for fertile land. It is also mentioned that in many cases their advantages, compared to land-mounted solar-PVs, offset their higher capital cost. The preliminary Greek National Plan for Energy and Climate has been published [28]. It is stated that in 2050 the installed power of solar power systems in Greece should be at 40.3 GW_p having a share at 53.3% in the total installed power of all the renewable energy systems in the country at 75.6 %. The possibility of installing FPVs in water dams of several hydropower plants in Greece has been studied [10]. The author stated that the integration of FPV systems in hydropower plants in Greece increases, by average, their initial capacity factor

by 42.32%. He also mentioned that by covering 9.39% of the water dams' surface with FPVs in ten Greek hydropower plants their installed hydropower capacity is increased by 100%.

USE OF FLOATING PHOTOVOLTAICS ON WATER BODIES

A new unconventional technology regarding the installation of solar-PV systems in water bodies is their floatation on the water surface. The majority of existing FPVs have been installed on fresh water man-made or natural reservoirs while their broad installation on the sea has not been developed so far. FPVs have several pros and cons compared to their installation on the ground and on rooftops of buildings. FPV technology has been taken-off during the last fifteen years particularly in densely populated countries facing land shortages. The global installation of FPV in several countries in 2021 is presented in table 1.

Table 1. Floating Photovoltaics Installed Globally in 2021

Country	%, globally
China	75.04
Japan	15.98
Korea	6.01
UK	1.98
Other	0.99
Total	100

Source: [1]

Floating photovoltaics have various benefits compared with ground-mounted photovoltaics and with solar-PVs installed on rooftop of buildings. The main disadvantage is their higher installation cost which in many cases is counterbalanced by their multiple benefits. The benefits of FPVs are presented in table 2.

Table 2. Benefits of Floating Photovoltaic Systems

1.	Utilization of existing electricity transmission infrastructure at hydropower sites
2.	Close proximity to demand centers (in the case of water supply reservoirs)
3.	Improved energy yield thanks to the cooling effects of water and the decreased presence of dust
4.	Reduced evaporation from water reservoirs, as the solar panels provide shade and limit the evaporative effects of wind
5.	Improvements in water quality, through decreased algae growth
6.	Reduction or elimination of the shading of panels by their surroundings
7.	Elimination of the need for major site preparation, such as leveling or the laying of foundations, which must be done for land-based installations
8.	Easy installation and deployment in sites with low anchoring and mooring requirements, with a high degree of modularity, leading to faster installations.

Source: [27]

The impacts of FPV on water quality and on the living organisms in water bodies have not been studied extensively and are not fully understood so far. The potential opportunities and threats of floating photovoltaics on water quality and on living organisms are presented in table 3.

Table 3. Potential Opportunities and Threats of Floating Photovoltaics on Water Quality

System	Opportunities	Threats
Physical	Reduced evaporation	
	Reduced water temperature	
	Reduced sedimentation	
	Continued horizontal mixing	
Chemical	Reduced salinity	Anoxia

		Nitrification
		Release of Methane
		Release of hydrogen Sulfide
		Release of Ammonia
		Release of heavy metals from bed sediments
Biological	Reduced algae growth	Algal biomass Peaks delayed
	Reduced Fecal Coliforms E. Coli Concentrations	Algal composition modified
		Large Algal blooms
	Reduced predator vigilance for fish	Success of blue-green algae improved
	Increased zooplankton	Reduced mixing and turbidity
		Fish die
		Shading affects fish feeding

Source: [1]

The technology of FPV is expected to grow rapidly in the near future particularly in countries and areas where: a) the population density is very high, b) there are conflicts regarding the land use for food production or other uses and energy generation, c) in countries and areas with water shortages taking into account the fact that FPVs reduce the water evaporation from water reservoirs.

POSSIBILITY OF USING FLOATING PHOTOVOLTAICS ON WATER BODIES IN CRETE

The island of Crete has several man-made water reservoirs and limited natural lakes including Kourna lake and the tiny Agia lake in the prefecture of Chania. The man-made water bodies in Crete with water capacity higher than 10 mil. M³ are presented in table 4. It should be mentioned that currently hydroelectricity plants do not exist in the island. Floating photovoltaics have not been installed so far in water reservoirs in Crete. It has been indicated that the installation of FPVs on two major water reservoirs in the island with coverage ratio 10% could generate 46.37 GWh_{el}/year which correspond at 1.52% of the annual power demand in Crete (*Vourdoubas, 2022*). Man-made water reservoirs have higher water capacity and larger surface than the small natural lakes in Crete which are part of fragile and protected ecosystems. Therefore, they should be preferred for the installation of FPVs. Taking into account that solar energy is foreseen to have a dominant role in green electricity generation by 2050 in Greece and that solar irradiance in Crete is abundant, solar-PV power generation should be promoted with different installation technologies including ground-mounted systems, agrivoltaics, photovoltaics installed on rooftop of buildings, vertical photovoltaics and floating photovoltaics. Solar-PV installed on rooftops of buildings and FPVs have the advantage that they do not use valuable land and conflicts related with competitive land uses are avoided. Conclusively, the installation of FPV in, preferably man-made, water reservoirs in Crete consists of a realistic option in the near future.

Table 4. Man-Made Water Reservoirs with Water Capacity Higher than 10 mil. m³ in Crete

Name	Location/prefecture	Capacity (mil. m ³)
Potamon	Rethymno	22.50
Aposelemi	Heraklion	25.27
Faneromeni	Heraklion	19.67
Mpramianon	Lasithiou	16
Plati Potamou	Rethymno	51
System of three dams	Chania	45
Dematiou	Heraklion	30
Agiou Ioanni	Lasithiou	18.5

Source: [3]

ASSESSMENT OF USING SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAICS IN KOURNA LAKE

Kourna lake is a rather small natural lake located in the western part of the island being part of a fragile and protected under Nature 2000 area. The lake is surrounded with cultivated land and olive tree groves. It is indicated in many tourist' guides as a worth-visited spot for visitors in the island and

various tavernas and restaurants have been developed in the surrounding area together with water activities. Several characteristics of Kourna lake are presented in table 5. Future installation of FPV on the lake's surface should take into account their impacts on water characteristics and on the living organisms. Existing studies have indicated that installation of FPVs with coverage ratio 2%-5% does not have any worth-mentioning impacts on water reservoirs (*Ilgen et al, 2023*). However, this must be also verified for Kourna lake. In any case the installation of FPV on the lake with coverage ratio higher than 5%-10% is not suggested. Any conflicts with local residents who have developed tourism activities in the lake should be avoided. It should be suggested that installing FPVs in the existing man-made water bodies in Crete is more appropriate and beneficial than installing them in Kourna lake.

Table 5. Characteristics of Kourna Lake

Characteristic	Value
Location	Prefecture of Chania, Crete, Greece
Area	58 ha
Max length	1.08 km
Max width	0.88 km
Max depth	22.5 m
Distance from the sea	2.5 km
Water volume	7,500,000 m ³
Height above the sea level	20 m
Number of fish and eel species in the lake	6

Source: [11], [24]

The potential impacts of floating photovoltaics on physical, chemical and biological characteristics in Kourna lake are presented in table 6.

Table 6. Potential Impacts of Floating Photovoltaics on Physical, Chemical and Biological Parameters in Kourna Lake

Parameter in the water body	Impact of floating photovoltaics
Water temperature	Decrease of water temperature, Unstable and shorter thermal stratification of the water
Dissolved oxygen concentration	Decrease
Water conductivity	Decrease
Total dissolved solids concentration	Decrease
Chlorophyll-a concentration	Decrease
Phosphorous concentration	There are not changes
Fish population	The impacts on fish population in large water bodies are insignificant
Plant and animal communities	Adverse impacts

Source: various authors

The electricity generation from floating photovoltaic modules installed on the surface of Kourna lake with coverage ratio 5% and 10% as well as their installation cost are presented in table 7.

Table 7. Electricity Generation from Floating Photovoltaic Modules Installed on the Surface of Kourna Lake with Coverage Ratio 5% and 10%

Surface of the lake	58 ha
Annual power generation from solar-PV systems in Crete	1,500 KWh/KW _p
Surface for installing 1 KW _p FPV	12 m ²
Nominal power of FPVs installed on the lake with coverage ratio 5% (surface 2.9 ha)	2.42 MW _p
Annual electricity generation from these FPVs	3,600 MWh
Average annual electricity consumption in households in Greece	4,000 KWh
Households which can meet their annual power demand with the electricity generated from FPVs	900
Installation cost of FPVs	1,300 €/KW _p

Cost of the FPV system	3.15 mil €
Nominal power of FPVs installed on the lake with coverage ratio 10% (surface 5.8 ha)	4.83 MW _p
Annual electricity generation from these FPVs	7,245 MWh
Annual power demand in Crete in 2018	3,043 GWh
% coverage of the power demand in Crete in 2018 with the generated electricity from the abovementioned FPVs	0.24 %
Households which can meet their annual power demand with the electricity generated from FPVs	1,800
Cost of the FPV system	6.3 mil €

Source: own estimations

ADVANTAGES AND DRAWBACKS OF USING FLOATING PHOTOVOLTAICS IN KOURNA LAKE

Installation of FPVs on the surface of Kourna lake has various advantages and drawbacks. The main advantages are related with the reduced water evaporation from the lake and the higher electricity yield due to the fact that the temperature in the solar panels is lower, compared to ground-mounted solar-PVs, due to their proximity with the water surface and its cooling. The main drawbacks are related with their higher installation cost, at around 10% - 15%, compared to the cost of ground-mounted photovoltaics and the potential and not fully understood impacts on water quality and on the living organisms in the lake. The low coverage ratio of the lake's surface with FPVs minimizes their impacts on the biotic and abiotic environment. Apart from the technical and economic advantages and drawbacks the potential social impacts on the local society should be taken into account. The installation of the FPV system in the lake should not create conflicts with the current tourism activities and consultation with the local stakeholders is necessary before making any decision. The advantages and drawbacks of installing FPV in Kourna lake are presented in table 8.

Table 8. Advantages and Drawbacks of Installing Floating Photovoltaics on Kourna Lake

Advantages	Drawbacks
Solar power is generated in the lake without using fertile land resulting in economic profit	The high humidity has adverse impacts on the solar panels
The water evaporation from the lake is reduced	The impacts of the FPV system on water quality are not well understood
The FPV system can be anchored easily in the lake	The impacts of the FPV system on aquatic life are not well known
The cooling effect on the solar panels results in higher electricity yield compared to ground-mounted solar-PV	The installation cost of the FPV system is around 10%-15% higher compared to ground-mounted solar-PVs
Less land area is used for power generation	Undesired impacts to local tourism activities
	Potential conflicts with the local communities

Source: own estimations

DISCUSSION

The possibility of using floating solar photovoltaics in Kourna lake, Crete, Greece has been studied. Use of FPVs on natural or man-made water reservoirs in Crete and in Greece has not been reported so far. Kourna lake is the only natural lake with fresh water in the island located in an idyllic environment dominated by olive tree groves which is protected under Natura 2000 regulations. Several hotels are located in the surrounding area and the lake is currently used for touristic activities. The installation of FPVs in the lake has several advantages and drawbacks which should be assessed. However, the lack of similar installations in water bodies in Greece makes difficult the assessment. Existing experience worldwide indicates that higher priority for the installation of FPV systems should be given to man-made water reservoirs including water dams in hydropower stations. The generation of solar electricity has positive economic impacts locally while it could create conflicts with local residents involved in tourism activities and it could also have adverse impacts on water characteristics and on the living organisms in the lake and in the broader area. The unknown impacts of the FPV system on lake's environment and on living organisms makes difficult the assessment of this novel solar energy system. Apart from its impacts on lake's natural environment

the possibility of having conflicts with the local society due to the tourism activities cannot be ignored. Further work should be focused on examining the attitude of the local residents and entrepreneurs, using appropriate questionnaires, regarding the installation of the abovementioned FPV system on Kourna lake which might affect their enterprises.

CONCLUSIONS

The possibility of installing floating photovoltaics in Kourna lake, Crete has been studied. Solar-PV installations on man-made or natural water bodies in Crete and in Greece have not been reported so far although there are many investors willing to proceed with this challenging novel technology. This lake is the only natural lake with fresh water in the island of Crete with water capacity 7.5 mil M³ located in an idyllic and environmentally protected area hosting several tourism activities. The surface of the lake is 58 ha while a FPV system with nominal power at 2.42 MW_p can be installed on its surface with coverage ratio 5% generating 3,600 MWh annually. If the coverage ratio of the surface is at 10% the nominal power of the installed FPV will be at 4.83 MW_p while the annually generated electricity will be at 7,245 MWh corresponding at 0.24% of the power demand in the island in 2018. The installation of FPV in Kourna lake has several advantages and drawbacks. The main drawbacks are related with the higher installation cost compared to ground-mounted photovoltaics, the unknown impacts on water characteristics and on the living organisms in the lake as well as the potential conflicts which might arise with the local community due to its involvement with tourism activities which might be affected from the installation of the FPV system. However, it is well accepted that if the coverage ratio of the lake's surface with floating solar modules is less than 5% the impacts on the abiotic and biotic environment in the lake will be insignificant.

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